

A Supplementary Content

A.1 Experimental Setups

A.1.1 Evaluation Metrics.

The *Edit Similarity* is a key metric for evaluating the **readability** of decompiled code, and it quantifies the similarity between the decompiled code and original code. Following the work of [2], we use edit distance, a standard metric employed in other neural approaches [17, 21], to define edit similarity. The result, $ES(A, B)$, is normalized by the length of the ground truth sequence, where a higher edit similarity indicates better readability of the decompiled code. Specifically, it is calculated as follows:

$$ES(A, B) = 1 - \frac{ED(A, B)}{L_B} \quad (3)$$

where A represents the prediction sequence, B represents the true sequence, L represents the length of the sequence, and $ED(A, B)$ represents the editing distance between A and B . Editing distance is also called Levenshtein distance, which means the minimum number of operations required to convert a sequence A to B . It is usually computed by dynamic programming, and its state transition equation is as follows:

$$ED(A_i, B_j) = \begin{cases} \max(L_A, L_B) & \min(L_A, L_B) = 0 \\ \min \begin{cases} ED(A_{i-1}, B_j) + 1 \\ ED(A_i, B_{j-1}) + 1 \\ ED(A_{i-1}, B_{j-1}) + 1 \end{cases} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

A.1.2 Baseline LLMs.

The LLMs we use for decompilation are as follows:

- LLM4Decompile [31], the most advanced decompilation LLM, built on DeepSeek-Coder. It supports both direct end-to-end decompilation and the refinement of Ghidra’s outputs, delivering significant improvements in readability and executability. In this paper, we compare with its direct decompilation version under the same parameter scale.
- GPT-4o [27], DeepSeek-V3 [8] and Qwen-plus [3], the top-performing general-purpose LLMs, renowned for their capabilities in complex language understanding and generation tasks. The DeepSeek-V3 has 671B parameters.
- FAE [11] utilizes debugging information to accurately align assembly code with source code at the statement level. And it is a 6.7B model in the work of [11].

A.2 Ablation Study

A.2.1 Ablation Study on general-purpose LLMs.

To ensure a fair and transparent evaluation of the individual contributions of each module in CIW—such as the CFG and Data Mapping (DM), we conduct additional ablation experiments to quantify the module effectiveness on general-purpose LLMs.

“w/o CFG” in Table 8 refers to the setting where our designed CFGs are replaced with raw assembly sequences. Overall, CIW consistently outperforms the “w/o CFG”. These ablation studies further demonstrate that the CFG feature is more effective than pure assembly encoding since its structured form aligns better with the LLM decompilation task, reducing the burden of modeling long-range dependencies and jump relations from linear sequences and

enhancing the LLM’s ability to capture program logic and generate more readable source code.

“w/o DM” in Table 9 refers to the setting where values are inlined directly into the assembly instructions instead of being represented through our Data Mapping. The ablation results demonstrate that our Data Mapping mechanism is more effective than direct value inlining. We attribute this improvement to the fact that our design provides more intuitive cues, which helps the LLM more effectively identify and align precise data information.

Table 10: CIW on LLM4Decompile (%)

Metric	O0	O1	O2	O3	AVG
Re-com	90.85	91.46	88.41	87.20	89.48
Re-exe	47.20	20.61	21.22	20.24	27.32
ES	38.21	24.94	17.01	19.47	24.91

A.2.2 LLM4Decompile inference with CIW. We supplement experiments with LLM4Decompile 1.3B+CIW on the HumanEval 64-bit dataset, and the results are shown in Table 10. By comparing with LLM4Decompile 1.3B in Table 2, we find that even when applied to other decompilation-specific models, CIW still plays a beneficial role in triggering knowledge useful for decompilation. Additionally, by comparing with CIM 1.3B+CIW in Table 2, we recognize that fine-tuning a decompilation-specific LLM (eg., CIM) with carefully constructed data is necessary.

A.3 Case Study

To qualitatively assess CIM’s performance, we conduct the case study. Full case study results and visual comparisons are provided in follows.

(1) Effectiveness of CIM

We evaluate CIM’s effectiveness through a qualitative comparison with three baselines: GPT-4o with CIW, DeepSeek-V3 with CIW, and Hex-Rays, using the -O1-compiled 32-bit binary of function r_deriv from the ExeBench test set (Fig. 5). While all methods correctly recover data object (which have no data mapping between memory addresses and data segments), CIM with CIW uniquely achieves both correctness and enhanced readability in reconstructing program logic.

As shown in Fig. 5(d), GPT-4o with CIW makes three critical errors: (1) hardcoding the `switch` condition (line 10) to 0 instead of deriving it from function $find_among_b$ ’s return value, (2) incorrectly checking for non-zero rather than negative values from function $slice_from_s$ in cases 2–6 of `switch`, and (3) misassociating function r_deriv ’s return logic solely with function $find_among_b$ (lines 6,36). DeepSeek-V3 with CIW exhibits similar issues, failing to reconstruct both the `switch` logic and proper return behavior (lines 6,29 in Fig. 5(c)). Even Hex-Rays (Fig. 5(e)), despite correctly reconstructing the program logic, introduces five misleading and irrelevant local variables, whereas the source code contains only two meaningful ones, substantially undermining the readability of the pseudocode. These consistent failures across diverse methods

Table 8: Ablation study for CFG on general-purpose LLMs(%)

Metric	Model	ExeBench 64-bit					Human-Eval 64-bit				
		O0	O1	O2	O3	AVG	O0	O1	O2	O3	AVG
Re-com	GPT-4o+CIW	87.27	83.63	82.72	91.91	83.88	97.47	91.08	94.27	84.71	91.88
	w/o cfg	84.81	82.00	80.99	78.86	81.67	96.20	92.36	92.36	87.90	92.21
	Deepseek-V3+CIW	90.63	84.79	85.71	84.47	86.40	94.94	88.54	85.35	82.17	87.75
	w/o cfg	89.48	76.61	75.28	72.05	78.36	95.57	89.81	87.90	83.44	89.18
	Qwen-plus+CIW	77.90	75.45	76.46	75.44	76.31	89.24	86.62	87.26	69.43	83.14
	w/o cfg	78.86	67.44	67.50	65.31	69.53	87.97	83.44	86.62	73.25	82.82
Re-exe	GPT-4o+CIW	35.17	18.29	14.78	14.23	20.62	43.67	27.39	20.38	17.20	27.16
	w/o cfg	30.88	16.12	14.09	13.16	18.56	37.97	12.74	13.38	9.55	18.41
	Deepseek-V3+CIW	50.07	29.79	24.31	23.63	31.95	68.99	42.68	43.31	38.22	48.30
	w/o cfg	46.13	22.45	18.64	17.02	26.06	67.62	33.76	36.94	30.57	42.22
	Qwen-plus+CIW	25.50	12.75	10.02	10.37	14.66	25.32	10.83	10.19	10.83	14.29
	w/o cfg	23.49	8.60	7.15	6.64	11.47	21.52	7.64	8.92	4.46	10.64
ES	GPT-4o+CIW	48.82	41.12	40.56	40.34	42.71	45.07	36.93	37.37	34.53	38.48
	w/o cfg	48.48	34.82	33.49	34.70	37.87	45.08	36.21	36.52	35.48	38.32
	Deepseek-V3+CIW	60.89	43.99	42.03	40.87	46.95	52.33	36.62	38.04	34.11	40.28
	w/o cfg	55.91	37.02	35.30	33.66	40.47	50.99	38.32	39.80	36.54	41.41
	Qwen-plus+CIW	50.94	39.72	38.39	37.81	41.71	44.09	36.10	35.43	31.66	36.82
	w/o cfg	47.44	33.61	32.35	31.41	36.20	42.50	34.15	34.43	32.07	35.79

Table 9: Ablation study for Data Mapping on general-purpose LLMs(%)

Model	Metric	ExeBench 64-bit					Human-Eval 64-bit				
		O0	O1	O2	O3	AVG	O0	O1	O2	O3	AVG
Re-com	GPT-4o+CIW	85.16	79.49	78.61	74.26	79.38	90.00	87.80	84.62	73.58	84.00
	w/o DM	80.75	72.47	72.50	75.60	75.33	85.00	80.49	69.23	67.92	75.66
	Deepseek-V3+CIW	91.05	83.43	81.67	80.43	84.15	92.50	75.61	74.36	71.70	78.54
	w/o DM	85.62	78.37	76.69	75.34	79.00	100.00	87.80	79.49	73.58	85.22
	Qwen-plus+CIW	76.10	71.07	73.61	67.29	72.02	80.00	78.05	66.67	47.17	67.97
	w/o DM	75.54	64.33	61.25	60.32	65.36	75.00	60.98	56.41	58.49	62.72
Re-exe	GPT-4o+CIW	36.35	9.83	7.50	6.17	14.96	22.50	19.51	23.08	13.21	19.58
	w/o DM	30.92	4.49	8.61	8.58	13.15	10.00	9.76	5.13	7.55	8.11
	Deepseek-V3+CIW	51.64	21.63	11.67	10.72	23.92	40.00	34.15	33.33	32.08	34.89
	w/o DM	40.88	13.20	12.20	8.58	18.71	50.00	17.07	30.77	22.64	30.12
	Qwen-plus+CIW	24.58	5.06	5.28	4.29	9.80	10.00	12.20	5.13	7.55	8.72
	w/o DM	21.86	3.37	4.88	4.83	8.73	7.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.88
ES	GPT-4o+CIW	49.48	33.18	33.21	32.23	37.03	41.59	36.15	37.19	31.79	36.68
	w/o DM	46.37	33.73	34.78	33.08	36.99	41.75	33.89	35.48	36.27	36.85
	Deepseek-V3+CIW	58.38	37.38	35.76	34.22	41.44	49.98	38.32	37.64	30.20	39.04
	w/o DM	51.13	34.79	34.53	32.94	38.35	48.89	41.03	36.69	31.99	39.65
	Qwen-plus+CIW	48.25	33.28	32.51	30.95	36.25	44.08	35.43	33.50	28.16	35.29
	w/o DM	45.18	33.21	32.87	31.41	35.67	42.16	32.91	31.85	28.45	33.84

highlight the difficulty of accurately recovering readable program logic from low-level assembly code.

In contrast, CIM with CIW (Fig. 5(b)) successfully addresses these failures through training on a novel dataset (CID). CIM-6.7B with

CIW achieves fully accurate reconstruction of: (1) the switch entry condition, (2) case logic in branches 2-6, and (3) function `r_deriv` return logic. Beyond basic correctness, CIM demonstrates superior code quality through: (a) adoption of modern coding conventions

Figure 5: An example of readable decompilation. Presented are the source code (a) of the case sample alongside the decompilations of CIM-6.7B with CIW (b), DeepSeek-V3 with CIW (c), GPT-4o with CIW (d), and Hex-Rays (e).

Figure 6: Qualitative example of the decompilations made by CIM with CIW and its variations that ablate different components. Presented are the source code (a) of the case sample alongside the decompilations of CIM-6.7B + CIW (b), CIM-6.7B + CIW w/o CFG (c), and CIM-6.7B + CIW w/o DM (d).

like “Early Return” (line 5) to reduce control flow complexity, (b) generation of meaningful variable names and types, and (c) elimination of unnecessary procedural variables. This dual achievement of logical accuracy and code quality stems from CIM’s core innovation

- moving beyond simple instruction translation to explicitly model programmer intent through comprehensive control flow analysis during training.

<pre> 1625 1 void __thiscall std::_Fac_tidy_reg_t::~_Fac_tidy_reg_t(std::_Fac_tidy_reg_t *this) 1626 2 { 1627 3 std::_Fac_node *v1; // ecx 1628 4 std::_Fac_node *v2; // esi 1629 5 1630 6 while (1) 1631 7 { 1632 8 v2 = 0Block; 1633 9 1634 10 if (!Block) 1635 11 { 1636 12 break; 1637 13 } 1638 14 1639 15 v1 = 0Block; 1640 16 Block = *(std::_Fac_node **)Block; 1641 17 1642 18 std::_Fac_node::~_Fac_node(v1); 1643 19 sub_402A62(v2); 1644 20 } 1645 21 } </pre>	<pre> 1683 1 void free_fac_nodes(void) 1684 2 { 1685 3 Fac_node *p; 1686 4 1687 5 while (fac_nodes) 1688 6 { 1689 7 p = fac_nodes; 1690 8 fac_nodes = fac_nodes->next; 1691 9 1692 10 p->~Fac_node(); 1693 11 free_bench(p); 1694 12 } 1695 13 } </pre>
(a)	(b)
<pre> 1646 1 void __fastcall sub_23C6(_QWORD *a1) 1647 2 { 1648 3 *a1 = 0LL; 1649 4 a1[1] = 0LL; 1650 5 a1[2] = 0LL; 1651 6 a1[3] = 0LL; 1652 7 a1[4] = 0LL; 1653 8 a1[5] = 0LL; 1654 9 } </pre>	<pre> 1696 1 void init_0000001(struct stack *stk) 1697 2 { 1698 3 stk->top = 0; 1699 4 stk->size = 0; 1700 5 stk->capacity = 0; 1701 6 stk->array = NULL; 1702 7 stk->min = 0; 1703 8 stk->min_capacity = 0; 1704 9 } </pre>
(c)	(d)

Figure 7: (a) shows the decompilation result of function 0x4029BB in *Clever Bird.exe* produced by Hex-Rays; (b) presents the corresponding decompilation result generated by CIM-6.7B; (c) shows the decompilation result of function 0x23c6 in *revvm* produced by Hex-Rays; and (d) presents the corresponding decompilation result generated by CIM-6.7B.

(2) Reasonableness of CIW

Our qualitative evaluation validates the CIW’s design by analyzing CIM-6.7B’s performance on the function *runHitch* (from ExeBench, compiled with -O0 for 32-bit architecture) through systematic ablation studies (Figure 6). The results reveal that CIM-6.7B with CIW produces correct decompilations, models with ablated variants exhibit distinct failure modes that underscore CIW’s careful component integration. When CIW without CFG information, CIM-6.7B introduces structural flaws, including an erroneous else branch that corrupts the value of `motor[servoHi tch]` (Fig. 6(c), lines 5-6), demonstrating that program logic reconstruction fundamentally requires CFG guidance. Conversely, the CIW without data mapping tables version maintains correct program logic but fails at data recovery, notably converting constant 128 to 1.0 (Fig. 6(d), line 4), revealing that data mapping tables is critical for data recovery.

These results validate CIW’s core design principle: high-quality decompilation demands simultaneous attention to both macro-level structural accuracy (via CFG analysis) and micro-level value precision (through data recovery). The success of CIM-6.7B with complete CIW, contrasted with the failures of ablated variants, demonstrates the necessity of its integrated component of CIW for producing behaviorally accurate decompilations.

A.4 Real-world Application

To validate the practical effectiveness of our CIM, we randomly select binaries such as *Clever Bird.exe* and *revvm* from reverse engineering challenges in past CTF competitions (XNUCA 2019 and hxp CTF 2021) and perform decompilation on them (as shown in Fig. 7). From the decompiled results of functions such as ‘0x4029BB’

in *Clever Bird.exe* and ‘0x23c6’ in *revvm*, it can be observed that our decompilation-specific LLM outperforms Hex-Rays in terms of variable/function renaming, structure representation, and overall code readability.